

Paper 34**ACHIEVEMENTS AND OUTCOMES OF
INNOVATIONS: A CASE STUDY OF THE FOOD
PROCESSING INDUSTRY****Mohammed Ridhwan, Nithesh Shetty**MBA Evening, 1st year, College of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, City
Campus, Pandeshwar, Mangalore – 575 001.**Abstract**

This study analyzes the role played by food processing industries in India. With the advent of planned economy from 1951 and the subsequent industrial policy followed by Government of India, both planners and Government earmarked special role for small-scale industries and medium scale industries in the Indian economy. As per the Ministry of Food Processing Industry as data source, the food processing sector is highly fragmented industry, it widely comprises of the following sub-segments: fruits and vegetables, milk and milk products, beer and alcoholic beverages, meat and poultry, marine products, grain processing, packaged or convenience food and packaged drinks. A huge number of entrepreneurs in this industry are small in terms of their production and operations, and are largely concentrated in the unorganized segment. India is the world's second largest producer of food after China but accounts for less than 1.5 per cent of international food trade. The total food production in India is likely to double in the next ten years and there is an opportunity for large investments in food and food processing technologies, skills and equipment, especially in areas of Canning, Dairy and Food Processing, Specialty Processing, Packaging and Frozen Food. India is a country of over 1.10 billion consumers, increasing urban population is also another factor for growth and there is a large untapped domestic market of consumers in the food processing sector.

Keywords: Innovations, Sales Growth, Organized Food Processing, Agriculture.**1. Introduction**

The term food processing refers to the task of value addition to the agricultural or horticultural produce which can be accomplished in different ways viz. grading, sorting and packaging of these things in a systematic manner. It helps in the preservation of food items by increasing their shelf life. It also leads to their qualitative up-gradation thereby magnifying their functional utility. It covers a diverse range of products from various sectors like agriculture, horticulture, plantation, animal husbandry and fisheries.

The Food Processing industry in India is undergoing a significant growth. Food processing industry accounts for 35% of our country's total food market and is ranked fifth in terms of production, consumption, export and expected growth. With increase in online food ordering, the food processing industry is witnessing an incredible growth. This growing demand beckons the question; is the industry equipped enough to match the supply? The food processing industry in India has a high concentration of unorganized segments, accounting for almost 75 per cent across all product categories.

2. Objectives

- To know the contribution to economy by Food processing industry
- To analyse the Benefits of Food processing industry
- To know the challenges faced by this industry

3. RESEARCH AND METHODOLOGY:

The proposed methodology is studies on the above said objectives are based on the secondary data. These projects consist of graphical representation obtained from secondary data.

4. Discussions:

The Food Processing industry plays prominent role in the Indian economy. Food processing has an important role to play in linking Indian farmers to consumers in the domestic and international markets. The industry engages approximately 1.77 million people in around 39,319 registered units with fixed capital of \$ 29.2 billion and aggregate output of around \$ 144.6 billion. Major industries constituting the Food processing industry are grains, sugar, edible oils, beverages and dairy products. The food processing industry is one of the largest industries in India and ranks fifth in terms of production, consumption and exports. The government through the Ministry of Food Processing Industries (MoFPI) is making all efforts to encourage investments in the business. It has approved proposals for joint ventures (JV), foreign collaborations, industrial licenses, and 100 per cent export oriented units.

5. Market Size

The Indian food and grocery market is the world's sixth largest, with retail market contributing about 70 per cent of the sales. The Indian food processing industry accounts for 32 per cent of the country's total food market, one of the largest industries in India and is ranked fifth in terms of production, consumption, export and expected growth. It contributes around 8.80 and 8.39 per cent of Gross Value Added (GVA) in Manufacturing and Agriculture respectively, 13 per cent of India's exports and six per cent of total industrial investment. The online food ordering business in India is in its nascent stage, but witnessing exponential growth. With online food delivery players like FoodPanda, Zomato, TinyOwl and Swiggy building scale through partnerships, the organised food business has a huge potential and a promising future. According to Annual Survey of Industries (ASI), the total number of registered food processing factories in the country is 37,175. Andhra accounts for 25% of the total

registered food processing units followed by Tamil Nadu (14%), Telangana (10%), Maharashtra (8%) and Punjab (7.5%).

The food industry in India has, in the last few years, seen a lot of foreign investment. The Department of Industrial Policies and Promotion (DIPP) states that India received around USD 7.54 billion FDI from April 2000 to March 2017. The CII has predicted that the food processing sector has the potential to attract around USD 33 billion FDI in the next ten years and also generate nine million person-days of employment.

To name a few giant investments in the industry:

1. Amazon, the global e-commerce giant, has plans to diversify its business by entering the Indian food retailing market and invest around USD 515 million in the next five years.
2. Parle Agro Pvt Ltd has kept its target to achieve an annual target of Rs. 5,000 crore by 2018, and to do so have launched new products like Frooti Fizz.
3. US-based Cargill Inc aims to grow its branded consumer business in India by two times by 2020.
4. Uber Technologies Inc has entered the food delivery service with its brand UberEATS.

6. Key sub-segments of the Food processing industry in India

6.1 Dairy

India is the world leader in milk production, producing around 146 million MT of milk. The Indian dairy market is amongst the largest and fastest growing markets in the world. Per capita availability of milk in India has reached 322 grams per day, higher than the world average of 293.7 grams per day. Changing lifestyle patterns, increasing disposable incomes and increasing health consciousness are the key growth drivers for milk and high value milk products in India. To tap this surging demand most dairy players have entered the processed dairy products market with introduction of value added products like ghee, flavored yogurt, butter (with variants), flavored milk, cheese etc. New value added dairy products, innovative packaging, cold chain and new technology for value added dairy product processing offer tremendous potential for technology suppliers, processors as well as service providers.

Uttar Pradesh is the highest milk producing state in India contributing around 18% to the total milk production, followed by Rajasthan, Andhra Pradesh, Gujarat and Punjab contributing 11%, 10%, 8% and 7% respectively.

6.2 Fruits & Vegetables

India is the second largest producer of the Fruits and Vegetables in the world with a production of 256 million MT. India is the world's largest producer of bananas, papaya, mangoes & guavas and the second largest producer of potatoes, green peas, cabbage and

cauliflower. India witnesses nearly 4.6-15.9% wastage in fruits and vegetables annually, due to lack of modern harvesting practices and inadequate cold chain infrastructure. Processing levels in F&V currently stand at close to 2%. This gives immense opportunity to invest in initiatives that help reduce wastage levels including adequate infrastructure (cold chain, processing infrastructure), R&D for processed food & packaging and innovative on farm preservation systems. India's location gives it the unique advantage of connectivity to Europe, the Middle East, Japan, Singapore, Thailand, Malaysia and Korea.

Maharashtra, Andhra Pradesh, Gujarat, Karnataka and Uttar Pradesh are the leading producers of fruits in India, having a combined share of around 50% in the total fruits production. For Vegetables, major producers include West Bengal, Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, Madhya Pradesh and Gujarat, together accounting for over 50% of the national production.

6.3 Meat & Poultry

India has the world's largest population of livestock and produces around 5.3 million MT of meat annually. Wastages in poultry are comparatively higher at 6.7%, while in meat it is 2.7%. The current processing levels in poultry are 6%, while for meat it stands at 21%. Poultry is a highly vertically integrated industry in India and matches the efficiency levels of many western countries. India is the largest producer of buffalo meat and 2nd largest producer of goat meat. Modern abattoirs, logistics, processing and cold chain infrastructure is a huge opportunity in India, given the changing preference of Indian consumers for clean and safe meat and meat products.

6.4 Marine products

India, with a production of 9.6 million MT is the second largest fish producer in the world. India is endowed with abundant geographical resources suited for both marine and inland fisheries. The wastage levels in inland fisheries are to the tune of 5.2%, while for marine fisheries they are close to 10.5%. Processing levels of marine food in India are at 23%. Traditional independent fish retailers still dominate the distribution channel of fish and seafood in India. However, retail volume sales via modern grocery retail channels like supermarkets and hypermarkets from a smaller base have grown rapidly in recent years, particularly in major cities. Processing of fish into canned and frozen forms is carried out mostly for exports. Besides, there is an increased demand for processed and ready-to-eat marine products in the domestic and overseas market. Huge opportunity exists in India for cold chain development for marine products, value added product development for domestic as well as export market as well as innovations in packaging for increased shelf life and product differentiation.

The top five states for fisheries production in India are Andhra Pradesh, West Bengal, Gujarat, Kerala and Tamil Nadu with a combined share of around 60% of the total fish production.

Inland Fish Production (6 Million MT): The top five states are Andhra Pradesh, West Bengal, Uttar Pradesh, Bihar and Odisha contributing close to 68% to freshwater aquaculture.

Marine Fish Production (3.5 Million MT): The top five states are Gujarat, Kerala, Maharashtra, Andhra Pradesh and Tamil Nadu, contributing close to 74% to the total production.

7. Employment opportunities

Food processing is a branch of food science, which exists from the prehistoric times. Food processing has certain methods and techniques used to transform raw ingredients into food for the consumption of humans and animals. For job opportunities in Indian Food Processing Industry the candidates should usually have a degree in B.Sc. in Home Science/ Food Technology/ Food Science, one should have passed 10+2 examinations with Physics, Chemistry and Biology as the main subjects. For M.Sc / Management, the minimum eligibility is a B.Sc. There are opportunities like Food technologists, technicians, bio technologists and engineers which are required in this industry for the practical application of the principles of many disciplines of science in the manufacturing or production, preservation and packaging, processing and canning of various food products.

It is seen that food products industry, compared to other industries has the largest number of factories and engages largest number of employees as well. Since with respect to fixed capital the food products industry does not figure in top five, it shows that this sector is highly labour intensive per unit of capital. Thus every unit of capital invested in food products industry employs largest number of persons as compared to other industries while generating almost as high the output levels as in other industries. In 2014-15, it constituted 12.77 % of employment generated in all registered factory sector. Unregistered food processing sector supports employment to 47.9 lakh workers as per the NSSO 2010-11 and constitutes 13.72% of employment in the unregistered manufacturing sector.

8. GROWTH DRIVERS

The growth in the sector can be expected to be driven by the food and grocery market, which currently ranks sixth in the world and contributes approximately 70 % to the total retail sales. India's strong 1.2 billion consumer base provides a well-established domestic market for the food processing industry in India. As the consumers in the country are becoming more health-conscious, the demand for nutritious food is growing proportionately. In addition, rising number of working women and nuclear families is resulting in high demand for ready-to-eat and frozen food. Thus, overall India's food value chain is poised to create multiple opportunities for investment and employment in storage infrastructure, farming, retail and quality control.

India is endowed with a strong raw material base to stimulate the growth of food processing industry. The country is first in terms of milk production with production close to 155.5 million MT in FY 2015-16 and second in terms of fruits and vegetables in the world with production of 256 million MT. It is also the largest producer of spices with 6.9 million tones of spices produced in the year 2015-16. The country is third in egg production, fifth in meat production and second in fish production in the world. The steady supply of raw materials and availability of cold storage infrastructure will complement the growth in sub-segments like dairy, horticulture, plantation, animal husbandry and fisheries. India's diverse agro-climatic zones allow the country to produce a variety of crops.

Year wise Export of Processed Food Products (US \$ Million)

Year	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17
Exports	31459.58	35898.06	38051.43	36171.92	29672.37	30871.47
(%)Growth		14.11%	6.00%	-4.94%	-17.97%	4.04%

Contribution of Food Processing Industry to India's GDP through manufacturing (FY16)**9. GOVERNMENT SUPPORT**

Under the Make in India initiative, the Government plans to stimulate growth in the Food Processing sector through the creation of a strong infrastructure, reduction of food wastage and promotion of Ease of Doing Business (EODB) measures. The FDI in trading and e-commerce of food products is allowed up to 100% through government approval route. Additionally, the 100% FDI policy through automatic route in the sector for manufacturing in India has resulted in inflows of USD 1.7 Billion during April 2014 to December 2016. With such an increased government support, food business giants such as Kelloggs, Ferrero and BSA International are all set to expand their footprint in India. India's geographical proximity to food importing regions such as Singapore, Middle East, Thailand, Europe, Korea and Malaysia will further boost exports in the future.

Furthermore, the Integrated Cold Chain and Value Addition Infrastructure scheme under MoFPI aims to build strong cold storage infrastructure for dairy, fish and horticultural

industry. The Food Processing industry is critical to India's growth and the government is focused on providing adequate impetus to the sector. A well-developed Food Processing sector will help facilitate crop diversification and generate employment opportunities. The introduction of modern processing techniques for food will result in improved shelf-life of the agricultural produce and ensure steady revenue to farmers. With the correct set of policy implementations and support, the industry can grow by leaps and bounds, taking India to a new position of strength and prosperity in the global economy.

10. Strength and Opportunities

10.1 Strong demand growth

The demand for processed food is increasing due to increasing disposable income, urbanization, young population and nuclear families; leading to changing lifestyle and increasing expenditure on health and nutritional foods.

10.2 Flourishing Farm Sector

India is bestowed with a diverse agro-climatic conditions; large agriculture sector with second largest producer of fruits and and vegetables; abundant livestock with largest production of milk; and cost competitiveness.

10.3 Increasing investments

The food processing sector is a sunrise sector and government sees it as a future driver of Indian economy. Government has launched various infrastructure development schemes to increase investments in food processing infrastructure. The government is also making an amicable FDI environment in this sector.

11. Threats or Weakness of the Indian Food Processing Sector

Despite of its large size, Indian food processing industry is still at a nascent stage compared to its potential. It is one of the sunrise sectors in the country. Of the country's total agriculture and food produce, only 2 percent is processed currently in comparison to 40% in countries such as Malaysia and Thailand. There are several challenges that need to be addressed. These challenges span across the entire value chain and are as follows:

11.1 Productivity Issues

A major area of concern is food production itself. Despite being an agrarian economy and one of the largest producers of vegetables, fruits, wheat etc, it is unfortunate that the productivity of crops is quite low relative to international standards.

11.2 Availability of Skilled Resources

Human resource development needs to cover the entire gamut from basic infrastructure, education, vocational and technical guidance to qualified professionals in the sector.

11.3 Supply Chain Deterrents

Long and fragmented supply chains leading to high wastage and high costs especially due to seasonality, perishability and variability of produce.

11.4 Deadlocks in Infrastructure

Indian export- related infrastructure for agri-produce is grossly inadequate, especially at sea ports and airports. More than 30 percent of the produce is lost due to poor post-harvesting facilities and lack of cold chain infrastructure.

11.5 Low Adherence to Quality Standards

Lack of basic standard and infrastructure for adhering to quality standards. Given the size of the industry, there is a huge gap in the availability of laboratories, trained manpower, and certification agencies.

11.6 Low level of Linkages between Industries

Low level of interaction between industry and research institutes are one of the major problems. In order to improve farm productivity, continuous introduction and implementation of innovative technologies calls for existence of a strong R& D network. While investments are being made in this regard, the efforts have not been as rewarding.

12. Conclusion

As an extended arm of the agriculture, the food processing sector has immense nutritional and food security benefits for a vastly populated country like India plagued with problems like hunger and malnutrition. The sector has immense employment generation capacity. India is one of the major exporters of processed food products and so the FPI earns significant export revenue for the country. In this competitive environment, India has a leading edge on account of cultivation of a wide variety of fruits and vegetables supported by India's climatic and geographic diversity. India is also blessed with a reasonable supply of cereals, grains, livestock, fish etc. India needs to go for technology up-gradation as well as innovation and diminish the adverse role of intermediaries and strengthen supply chain for the robust growth of this sector. A vibrant FPI sector marked by a supportive ecosystem can alleviate India's concerns on inter-linked issues of food security, malnutrition and food inflation. And this must be a core priority for the government in the larger national interest.

.REFERENCES

- [1] A Journey through Indian Food Processing sector 2017 – MoFPI.
- [2] Food Processing Industry in India: Unleashing the Potential of the Non-alcoholic Beverage Sector (2014) - Arpita Mukherjee
- [3] Future Prospects for Indian Food Processing Industry- Mukund Kumar (2012)
- [4] Indian Food Processing Industry - Some Perspectives - Balakrishna AV (2008)
- [5] ASSOCHAM. (2015). Make in India: Pressing the Pedal.
- [6] Economics knowledge Banking, Yes Bank and Associated Chamber of Commerce and Industry in India (2015).
- [7] Stats Retrieved from <http://apeda.gov.in>